

STUDIES ON THE DEPENDENCE OF OPTICAL ACTIVITY ON CHEMICAL
CONSTITUTION. PART XLIV. THE ROTATORY DISPERSION OF
o-, *m*-, *p*-CHLOROPHENYLIMINO-*d*-CAMPHORS AND PHENYL-,
o-, *m*-, *p*-CHLOROPHENYLAMINO-*d*-CAMPHORS

BY BAWA KARTAR SINGH AND (MISS) SHANTI KUMARI SETHI

The rotatory dispersion of *o*-, *m*-, *p*-chlorophenylimino-*d*-camphors and phenyl-, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-chlorophenylamino-*d*-camphors has been determined in seven solvents and is found to obey one-term Drude's equation. It is therefore simple.

The effect of solvent and of position isomerism of substituent groups in benzene ring on the rotatory power of these compounds has been discussed.

The effect of conjugated double bonds on rotatory power, which is phenomenal in this series of compounds, as well as the 'characteristic' absorption bands (λ_c) have also been discussed.

In previous investigations of these compounds (Forster and Thornley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 942; Singh *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1919, 115, 572; this *Journal*, 1950, 28, 229) the rotatory power of *p*-chlorophenylimino-*d*-camphor was recorded in one solvent for one wave-length (N_{D_0}) only, whereas that of *m*- and *o*-chlorophenylimino-*d*-camphor was recorded in two solvents for N_{D_0} wave-length. In the case of the corresponding amino derivatives, the rotatory power of the *p*-chlorophenylamino-*d*-camphor was determined in one solvent for N_{D_0} line only. In the present investigation we have determined the rotatory powers of *o*-, *m*-, *p*-chlorophenylimino-*d*-camphors and phenyl-, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-chlorophenylamino-*d*-camphors in seven solvents for thirteen wave-lengths in the visible region of the spectrum ($\lambda = 6708\text{\AA}$ to $\lambda = 4358\text{\AA}$).

It may be recalled that Singh, Basu-Mallick and Bhaduri (this *Journal*, 1931, 8, 95) determined the rotatory power of phenylimino-*d*-camphor for three wave-lengths, and of phenylamino-*d*-camphor for four wave-lengths in six solvents. Singh and Singh (*ibid.*, 1951, 28, 229) later determined the rotatory dispersion of these compounds: whereas these values of rotatory dispersion agree in the case of phenylimino-*d*-camphor, they, however, do not agree for phenylamino-*d*-camphor. Our present values of rotatory dispersion of phenylamino-*d*-camphor agree with those of Singh, Basu-Mallick and Bhaduri (*loc. cit.*).

Nature of Rotatory Dispersion

These compounds exhibit 'simple' rotatory dispersion as their rotatory powers can be expressed by Drude's one-term equation,

$$[\alpha]_{\lambda}^c = \frac{k}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2}$$

where k is the rotation constant and λ_0^2 , the dispersion constant. The calculated values of rotatory dispersion (c) for different wave-lengths agree with the observed ones (o). The differences ($o-c$) are of the nature of casual experimental errors and have been omitted from Tables I-VII for economy of space. Out of 532 observations of rotatory power, 69 exactly agree with the calculated values,

387 agree within $\pm 0.02^\circ$ of the observed angle of rotation, 64 within 0.04° and the remaining 12 within $\pm 0.05^\circ$. The above mentioned cases, in which the differences between the observed and calculated values of rotatory power agree within $\pm 0.04^\circ$ to $\pm 0.05^\circ$ of the observed angle of rotation, are for wave-lengths in blue and blue-violet regions of the visible spectrum.

In Drude's equation, k may be taken as a measure of the *absolute* rotation of the compound for that value of the wave-length for which $\lambda = \sqrt{1 + \lambda_0^2}$. The *absolute* rotation constant, k , is thus numerically, but not dimensionally, identical with the specific rotation, $[\alpha]$. A comparison of rotatory powers, $[\alpha]$, and rotation constants, k , at this wave-length λ (where $\lambda = \sqrt{1 + \lambda_0^2}$) may be regarded as that for the corresponding conditions of wave-lengths in which the effects of dispersion are eliminated. This wave-length is in the near infra-red and is not much greater than 10,000 Å.

Position Isomerism and Rotatory Power

In the Tables A and B the sequence of specific rotatory powers, $[\alpha]_{\lambda_0}^{25}$, rotation constants, k , and the 'characteristic' wave-lengths, λ_0 , of phenyl-, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-chlorophenylimino-*d*-camphors (Table A) and phenyl-, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-chlorophenyl-amino-*d*-camphors (Table B) is given in the increasing order of their values.

TABLE A

Solvent.	$[\alpha]_{\lambda_0}^{25}$	k	λ_0
Benzene	$0 < m < p < un$	$0 < m < p < un$	$0 < m < p < un$
Chloroform	$0 < m < p < un$	$0 < m < p < un$	$0 < un < m < p$
Ethyl acetate	$0 < m < p$	$0 < m < p$	$0 < p < m$
Pyridine	$0 < m < p < un$	$0 < m < p < un$	$0 < un < p < m$
Acetone	$0 < m < p < un$	$0 < m < p < un$	$0 < un < m < p$
Ethyl alcohol	$0 < m < p < un$	$0 < m < p < un$	$0 < un < m < p$
Methyl alcohol	$0 < m < p < un$	$0 < m < p < un$	$0 < un < m < p$

TABLE B

Solvent.	$[\alpha]_{\lambda_0}^{25}$	k	λ_0
Benzene	$0 < p < m < un$	$0 < p < m < un$	$un < p < o < m$
Chloroform	$0 < p < m < un$	$0 < p < m < un$	$p < o < un < m$
Ethyl acetate	$p < o < m < un$	$p < o < m < un$	$m < o < p < un$
Pyridine	$m < p < un < o$	$m < p < un < o$	$p < o < un < m$
Acetone	$0 < p < m < un$	$0 < p < m < un$	$m < p < un < o$
Ethyl alcohol	$0 < p < m < un$	$0 < p < m < un$	$p < un < m < o$
Methyl alcohol	$0 < p < m < un$	$0 < p < m < un$	$p < m < un < o$

These tables show that neither Frankland's 'lever-arm hypothesis' (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1896, 89, 284), nor its electrostatic modification by Rule (*ibid.*, 1924, 125, 1122), according to both of which the *meta* isomeride should be intermediate between the *ortho* and *para*, and the unsubstituted compound should be equal to, or less than the *ortho* compound as regards their rotatory effects, is followed even in a single case. On the other hand, Cohen's rule (*ibid.*, 1910, 97, 1739) which states that the rotatory power produced by a *ortho* substituent differs more from that

of the *unsubstituted* compound, than do those of *meta* and *para* isomerides, is observed in all cases with the exception of chlorophenylamino-*d*-camphors in pyridine and ethyl acetate.

It is, however, worthy of note that the specific rotatory powers of the *ortho*-chlorophenylimino-*d*-camphor are remarkably lower than those of the *meta*, *para* and unsubstituted compounds (Table C).

TABLE C

Specific rotatory powers, $[\alpha]_{5461}^{25}$, in different solvents.

Structural formula.	Benzene. [2.28]*	CHCl ₃ . [5.2]	EtAc. [6.11]	Pyridine. [12.4]	Acetone. [21.5]	EtOH [25.8]	MeOH [31.1]
1. §R = N- †	927.2 (123.8)	871.5 (131.6)	...	910.3 (139.6)	815.8 (119.3)	841.3 (128.4)	800.8 (123.4)
2. RH-NH-	155.0 (37.15)	143.0 (31.31)	124.5 (25.79)	65.5 (14.73)	121.0 (28.5)	119.0 (28.66)	115.0 (27.48)
3. R=N-	190.0 (35.17)	188.3 (38.21)	208.5 (40.13)	305.0 (49.12)	253.2 (41.56)	203.3 (35.19)	220.0 (43.77)
4. RH-NH-	73.5 (15.57)	109.5 (24.71)	106.5 (24.76)	75.0 (16.05)	98.0 (21.65)	87.0 (20.07)	79.0 (15.84)
5. R=N-	656.0 (94.33)	624.0 (91.69)	596.0 (80.41)	710.0 (84.58)	574.8 (81.5)	598.3 (85.55)	553.3 (78.27)
6. RH-NH-	126.5 (26.55)	139.0 (28.34)	123.5 (29.94)	46.5 (9.96)	107.5 (26.76)	107.0 (25.56)	103.0 (25.815)
7. R=N-	838.0 (114.4)	865.0 (117.82)	740.0 (102.2)	852.0 (116.6)	729.9 (100.86)	758.0 (102.74)	726.6 (99.5)
8. RH-NH-	120.0 (25.86)	118.0 (26.04)	105.0 (23.58)	54.5 (12.206)	102.0 (24.57)	98.0 (24.42)	93.0 (24.784)

* The figures in square brackets indicate dielectric constant of pure solvents.

† The values in simple brackets are the rotation constants, k .

§ R represents C_9H_{14}

‡ The values of rotatory dispersion of phenylimino-*d*-camphor have been taken from Singh and Singh (this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 229).

TABLE D

Molecular rotatory powers, $[M]_{D}^{25}$, in different solvents.

*Substance.	Benzene.	Chloroform.	Ethyl acetate.	Pyridine.	Acetone.	KNO ₃ .	MeOH.
	Diff.	Diff.	Diff.	Diff.	Diff.	Diff.	Diff.
3.	523.5	518.8	573.8	840.3	667.7	561.1	606.0
	319.5	314.8	278.2	612.1	435.8	318.7	386.7
4.	204.0	304.0	295.6	208.2	271.9	211.4	219.3
5.	1807.0	1719.0	1642.0	1956.0	1583.0	1628.0	1524.0
	1455.9	1333.2	1399.3	1827.0	1384.6	1351.0	1338.1
6.	351.1	385.8	342.7	139.0	298.4	297.0	285.9
7.	2308.0	2383.0	2039.0	2347.0	2010.0	2088.0	2002.0
	1972.2	2052.8	1744.8	2195.8	1721.4	1816.1	1743.9
8.	335.8	330.2	294.2	151.2	288.6	271.9	258.4
1.	2835.0	2100.0	---	2194.0	1966.0	2032.0	1930.0
	1902.1	1752.6	---	2034.8	1671.9	1711.8	1650.5
2.	332.9	347.4	322.5	159.2	294.1	289.1	279.5

* The number of the substances corresponds to those recorded in Table C.

TABLE E

Characteristic wave-lengths (λ_0) in $\text{\AA}$

Substance.	Benzene.	CHCl_3	EtAc.	Pyridine.	Acetone.	HtOH.	MeOH.	Average.
$\text{R}=\text{N}-\langle \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \rangle^\dagger$	4051	3815	...	3806	3899	3821	3798	3888
$\text{RH}-\text{NH}-\langle \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \rangle$	2648	2821	3028	2896	2543	2395	2328	2848, 2417.
$\text{R}=\text{N}-\langle \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl} \rangle$	3645	3085	3254	3697	3663	3535	3152	3535, 3164
$\text{RH}-\text{NH}-\langle \text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{Cl} \rangle$	2963	2679	2574	2921	2775	2668	3128	2946, 2640
$\text{R}=\text{N}-\langle \text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{Cl} \rangle$	3925	3889	4036	4241	3935	3911	3953	3984
$\text{RH}-\text{NH}-\langle \text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{Cl} \rangle$	2971	3061	2392	3017	2381	2442	2159	3016, 2405, 2159
$\text{R}=\text{N}-\langle \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl} \rangle$	4021	4024	4012	4017	4000	4034	4017	4018
$\text{RH}-\text{NH}-\langle \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl} \rangle$	2893	2402	2766	2724	2119	2228	1733	2794, 2360, 1734
$\text{R}=\text{N}-\langle \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3 \rangle^\dagger$	3990	3802	—	3851	3822	3845	4082	3952
$\text{R}=\text{N}-\langle \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3 \rangle^\dagger$	3930	3987	—	3918	3886	3962	4014	3950
$\text{R}=\text{N}-\langle \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3 \rangle^\dagger$	4246	3954	—	4130	3869	3947	4096	4040
$\text{R}=\text{N}-\langle \text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{CH}_3 \rangle^*$	3407	3304	—	3196	3274	3194	3239	3269

TABLE E (contd.)

	Benzene.	CHCl ₃ .	EtAc.	Pyridine.	Acetone.	EtOH.	MeOH.	Average.
RH - NH-	<u>3164</u>	3501	—	3497	<u>3264</u>	<u>3268</u>	<u>3186</u>	3454, <u>3221</u>
R=N-	<u>3206</u>	<u>3164</u>	—	3514	3584	3472	<u>3445</u>	3523, <u>3205</u>
RH - NH-	3180	3181	—	3180	3317	3214	3228	3217
R=N-	3701	<u>3305</u>	—	3547	3548	<u>3347</u>	<u>3227</u>	3593, <u>3293</u>
RH - NH-	<u>3187</u>	3461	—	<u>3162</u>	<u>3194</u>	<u>3164</u>	<u>3178</u>	3464, <u>3177</u>

† Singh and Singh, *this Journal*, 1951, 28, 229.

* Singh and Kapur, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1949, 29A, 413.

‡ Singh and Kapur, *ibid.*, 1950 31A, 280.

R represents C_8H_{14}

The sequence of rotation constants, k 's, in the decreasing order of their values is the same as that of the specific rotatory powers, $[\alpha]_{D}^{20}$. The order of the increasing value of the characteristic wave-lengths, λ_0 , for the different isomerides, does not, however, run parallel to that of the other two constants, namely, $[\alpha]_{\lambda}^{20}$ and k (Tables A and B). The numerical values of these constants do not show any relationship (Tables I to III).

Influence of Solvent on Rotatory Power

Table C shows that the sequence of increase in rotatory power with decrease in dielectric constant of the solvent is in no case followed in the whole series. In fact, it would be more rational to compare the values of rotatory powers with the dielectric constants of the solutions, which are not available.

The Effect of Conjugated Unsaturation on Rotatory Power

The molecular rotatory powers, $[M]_{D}^{25}$, of the chlorophenylimino-*d*-camphors and chlorophenylamino-*d*-camphors are shown in Table D for seven solvents. The fall in molecular rotation, $[M]_{D}^{25}$, in passing from the arylimino-*d*-camphor to arylamino-*d*-camphor is also shown. The remarkable fall in the molecular rotatory powers of aryliminocamphors on their reduction to arylamino compounds may be correlated with a break (dotted line) in the conjugation of the double bonds of the carbonyl, azethenoid and phenyl groups present in the arylimino derivatives, thus :

It is remarkable that the fall in rotation is most in *para*-substituted compounds and least in the *ortho*-substituted ones. The fall in the case of unsubstituted compounds is intermediate between those of *para* and *meta* derivatives.

*The Influence of Solvent, Nature and Position of the Substituent Groups in the Benzene, Naphthalene and Quinoline Rings, and the Effect of Conjugated Double Bonds present in the Molecule of the Optically Active Compounds on the 'Characteristic' Wave-length (λ_0) in the Ultraviolet Region : Correlation between λ_0 and $\lambda_{(\max)}$.
The 'Characteristic' Ultraviolet Absorption Maximum*

In Table E are recorded the 'characteristic' wave-lengths (λ_0 's), governing the rotatory power, deduced from Drude's one-term equation, in the following 17 optically active compounds, namely, phenyl-, chlorophenyl- (*o*-, *m*-, *p*-), tolyl- (*o*-, *m*-, *p*-), naphthyl- (α - and β -) and quinolinoimino-*d*-camphors and phenyl-, chlorophenyl- (*o*-, *m*-, *p*-), naphthyl- (α - and β -), and quinolinoamino-*d*-camphors.

The compounds listed in Table E fall into two groups: the arylimino- and the arylamino *d*-camphors. In the former series the conjugation between the double bonds of the carbonyl, azethenoid and the phenyl (or aryl) groups of the chromophore,

is complete.

In the case of phenyl-, chlorophenyl- (*m*-, *p*-), and tolyl- (*o*-, *m*-, *p*-)imino-*d*-camphors, the average value of the 'characteristic' wave-length (λ_0) of the chromophore is about $3972\text{\AA}$, but in the case of *o*-chlorophenylimino-*d*-camphor it is considerably less, λ_0 's being 3635 and $3164\text{\AA}^*$. In the case of naphthyl- (α - and β -) and quinolinoimino-*d*-camphors, there are two 'characteristic' wave-lengths, 3558 and $3256\text{\AA}$. The values of λ_0 of this chromophore are, thus, lowered by the substitution of the naphthyl or quinolyl radical in place of phenyl group.

* The values of λ_0 's are the average of the series in different solvents.

In the case of camphorquinone, the average value of the 'characteristic' wave-length (λ_0) in six solvents in 1% solution at 35° is 4740 Å (Singh, Basu-Mallick and Bhaduri, *loc. cit.*), whereas Lowry and Cutter report $\lambda_0 = 4730$ Å in 15% benzene solution at 20° (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 607).

The chromophore of camphorquinone is also present in glyoxal, whose 'characteristic' absorption maxima (λ_{max}) are 1960 2800 and 4630 Å. Lowry and French (*ibid.*, 1924, 128, 1921) record the 'characteristic' absorption maxima of camphorquinone as below :

Solvent.	Conc.	Log ϵ .	λ_{max} .
Alcohol	M/150	1.46	4650
Benzene	M/250	1.55	4650
"	15 g./100 c.c.	...	4700

The value of the 'characteristic' wave-length of this compound, as mentioned above ($\lambda_0 = 4740$ Å), deduced from the rotatory dispersion equation of Drude (Singh, Basu-Mallick and Bhaduri, *loc. cit.*), is, thus, practically identical with the ultraviolet absorption maximum ($\lambda_{max} = 4700$ Å). In the case of camphor, Lowry and French (*loc. cit.*) report the following values for the 'characteristic' ultraviolet absorption maxima (λ_{max}):

Solvent.	Conc.	Log ϵ .	λ_{max} .	* λ_0 .
Alcohol	M/100	1.67	2880	2950, 1924
cycloHexane	M/100	1.45	2880	...
"	20 g / 100 c.c.	...	2900	...
Benzene	7 g / 100 c.c.	1.57	2880	2920, 2283

* Taken from Singh *et al.* (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1935, 2A, 378 ; 1947, 26A, 263).

The agreement between the values of λ_{max} and λ_0 is, thus, very close.

It is therefore clear that there is sufficient evidence to show that the 'characteristic' wave-lengths (λ_0) deduced from Drude's rotatory dispersion equation are in agreement with those obtained by the direct measurements of the 'characteristic' ultraviolet absorption maxima (λ_{max}).

Ox reduction of the azethenoid group of the arylimino-camphors, the conjugation between the double bonds of this group with those of the carbonyl and the aryl groups is broken, resulting in a new chromophore,

in which the optimum association of double bonds is no longer present. It is accompanied by not only a phenomenal depression of the rotatory powers, as pointed out above, but also by a great fall in the value of λ_0 from about 3900-4000 Å to about 2800-2900 Å, pertaining to the keto group, in the case of phenyl- and chlorophenyl-imino-*d*-camphors. There are also lower 'characteristic' wave-lengths at about 2200-2400 and 1734 Å, associated with this chromophore. On the other hand, in the case of naphthyl and quinolino derivatives, the chromophore has the following values of the λ_0 :

The 'characteristic' wave-lengths (λ_c) associated with the above mentioned chromophores containing the azethenoid linking are lower (3500–3600 $\text{\AA}$ and 3200–3300 $\text{\AA}$) than those of the chromophores of phenyl- and substituted phenyliminocamphors (3900–4000 $\text{\AA}$). It must be ascribed to the different aryl groups present in these compounds. On the whole, there is a very small lowering in the 'characteristic' wave-lengths associated with the chromophore of these compounds, when the azethenoid group is replaced by the alkylamino group. The 'characteristic' wave-length of the keto group ($\lambda_c = 2800\text{--}2900 \text{ \AA}$) has disappeared and is replaced by two 'characteristic' wave-lengths at about 3450 and 3200 $\text{\AA}$.

FIG. 1

TABLE I
o-Chlorophenylimino-*d*-camphor.

Solvents:	MeOH.	EtOH.	Acetone.	Pyridine.	EtAc.	CHCl ₃ .	Benzene.
Conc. (g./100 c.c.):	0.3000	0.3000	0.3000	0.3000	0.3000	0.3000	0.3000
Calc. $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \lambda_D \\ [\alpha] \end{array} \right\}$	$\frac{43.77}{\lambda^2 - 0.09947}$	$\frac{35.19}{\lambda^2 - 0.1951}$	$\frac{41.56}{\lambda^2 - 0.1342}$	$\frac{49.23}{\lambda^2 - 0.1367}$	$\frac{40.13}{\lambda^2 - 0.1059}$	$\frac{38.21}{\lambda^2 - 0.0953}$	$\frac{31.17}{\lambda^2 - 0.1329}$
λ_D	0.3134 ₃	0.3336	0.3663	0.3697	0.3254	0.3685	0.3645
Lines.	$\left. \begin{array}{l} [\alpha]_D \\ 0 \end{array} \right\}$						
Liqns	125.0	108.3	131.6	155.0	116.5	108.3	98.3
	124.89	108.3	131.6	156.8	116.6	107.6	98.3
C ₆ H ₆	136.6	121.6	148.3	175.0	130.0	120.0	116.6
	138.90	121.6	148.2	176.8	130.0	119.7	116.6
Liqns	160.0	141.6	175.0	208.3	151.6	138.3	131.6
	160.03	141.6	174.4	208.3	150.5	137.8	130.1
Na ₂ SO ₄	178.3	158.3	195.0	233.3	166.6	151.6	145.0
	177.49	158.4	195.1	233.3	166.3	151.7	145.5
Hgns	186.6	168.3	210.0	250.0	173.3	160.0	155.0
	186.56	168.4	208.4	248.8	175.8	159.9	155.0
Agns	220.0	201.6	251.6	301.6	208.3	188.3	190.0
	219.38	202.4	252.2	303.6	207.8	187.5	187.7
Hgns	240.0	203.3	253.3	305.0	208.3	188.3	190.0
	240.20	203.3	253.3	304.2	208.3	188.2	188.7
Agns	255.0	238.5	303.3	365.0	241.6	215.0	223.6
	254.67	240.6	303.1	365.0	242.5	217.0	225.3
C ₆ H ₆	275.0	275.00	...	...	...	...	...
	275.00	275.00	...	...	...	...	...

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TABLE II
m-Chlorophenylimino-d-camphor.

Solvent: Conc. (g/100 c.c.):	MeOH. 0.3000		EtOH. 0.3000		Acetone. 0.5000		Pyridine. 0.5000		EtAc 0.5000		CHCl ₃ . 0.3333		Benzene. 0.3000	
	Calc. [α] λ _D	[α] c	Calc. [α] λ _D	[α] c	Calc. [α] λ _D	[α] c	Calc. [α] λ _D	[α] c	Calc. [α] λ _D	[α] c	Calc. [α] λ _D	[α] c	Calc. [α] λ _D	[α] c
	78.27 λ _D ²⁰ = 0.3953		85.55 λ _D ²⁰ = 0.1550		81.3 λ _D ²⁰ = 0.1569		84.58 λ _D ²⁰ = 0.1789		80.41 λ _D ²⁰ = 0.1629		91.69 λ _D ²⁰ = 0.1513		94.33 λ _D ²⁰ = 0.1541	
Lines.	[α] c	[α] c	[α] c	[α] c	[α] c	[α] c	[α] c	[α] c	[α] c	[α] c	[α] c	[α] c	[α] c	[α] c
L ₁ H ₁ H ₂	266.6	256.4	290.0	290.0	278.0	277.4	312.0	312.0	280.0	280.1	307.5	307.0	319.0	318.8
C ₂ H ₂ H ₃	305.0	303.1	331.3	329.7	313.3	314.5	359.0	359.0	320.0	319.7	349.0	348.3	351.0	352.1
L ₂ H ₁ H ₂	350.0	351.8	391.6	393.6	378.0	377.1	437.0	435.9	382.0	383.7	414.0	414.5	430.5	431.8
N ₁ H ₂ H ₃	410.3	409.9	444.6	445.2	427.0	427.2	502.0	502.5	435.0	436.1	468.0	468.0	490.0	488.4
A ₁ H ₂ H ₃	440.0	439.9	478.0	477.7	459.0	458.7	545.0	545.0	468.2	469.8	500.5	500.5	522.0	520.4
A ₂ H ₂ H ₃	546.6	548.3	593.3	593.9	573.0	572.1	703.0	704.4	590.0	591.0	618.5	620.7	648.0	646.5
H ₁ H ₂ H ₃	553.3	551.4	598.3	597.5	574.8	575.4	710.0	709.1	596.0	594.4	624.0	624	656.0	654.5
A ₂ H ₁ H ₃	678.3	680.3	735.0	735.7	720.0	710.8	917.0	915.4	745.2	743.5	765.0	764.0	805.0	804.6
C ₁ H ₁ H ₂	748.6	746.6	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...

TABLE III
p-Chlorophenylimino-*d*-camphor.

Solvent:	MeOH.	EtOH.	Acetone.	Pyridine.	EtAc.	CHCl ₃	Benzene.	
Conc. (g./100 c.c.):	0.3000	0.3000	0.4140	0.5000	0.4140	0.4140	0.5000	
Calc. $\left. \begin{array}{l} [\alpha]_D^{20} \\ \lambda_D \end{array} \right\} = \frac{59.5}{\lambda^2 - 0.1614}$		$\frac{102.74}{\lambda^2 - 0.1638}$	$\frac{100.86}{\lambda^2 - 0.1600}$	$\frac{116.6}{\lambda^2 - 0.1614}$	$\frac{102.2}{\lambda^2 - 0.1610}$	$\frac{117.82}{\lambda^2 - 0.1620}$	$\frac{114.4}{\lambda^2 - 0.1617}$	
λ_D	0.4017	0.4034	0.4000	0.4017	0.4012	0.4024	0.4021	
Lines.	[α]	[α]	[α]	[α]	[α]	[α]	[α]	
Lines	331.6 333.2 358.9 357.5 408.3 408.0 490.0 489.7 555.8 556.9 600.0 599.8 750.0 754.1	358.9 357.5 408.3 408.0 490.0 489.7 555.8 556.9 600.0 599.8 750.0 754.1	347.8 347.7 404.0 404.1 484.2 485.7 552.0 552.5 630.0 627.6 674.0 675.7 724.8 725.6	404.0 404.1 484.2 485.7 552.0 552.5 630.0 627.6 674.0 675.7 724.8 725.6 842.0 841.4	353.9 353.7 402.1 403.2 484.5 483.3 549.8 548.9 591.8 590.5 746.0 744.9 852.0 851.5	409.4 408.9 485.0 466.3 560.3 559.5 635.0 636.5 684.0 684.4 858.2 859.6 945.6 946.6	397.0 396.8 466.3 453.0 541.6 541.6 616.0 616.6 662.0 663.6 833.0 833.2 938.0 938.1	0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
Lines	391.7 393.1 471.6 471.3 535.0 535.5 576.6 576.4 723.3 723.1 726.6 727.3 905.2 905.1	391.7 393.1 471.6 471.3 535.0 535.5 576.6 576.4 723.3 723.1 726.6 727.3 905.2 905.1	397.2 396.3 453.0 450.8 492.1 493.2 560.3 559.5 635.0 636.5 684.0 684.4 858.2 859.6	453.0 450.8 492.1 493.2 560.3 559.5 635.0 636.5 684.0 684.4 858.2 859.6 945.6 946.6	492.1 493.2 560.3 559.5 635.0 636.5 684.0 684.4 858.2 859.6 945.6 946.6 1078.0 1077.0	466.3 453.0 541.6 541.6 616.0 616.6 662.0 663.6 833.0 833.2 938.0 938.1 1044.0 1043.0	453.0 453.5 541.6 541.6 616.0 616.6 662.0 663.6 833.0 833.2 938.0 938.1 1044.0 1043.0	0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0

TABLE IV

o-Chlorophenylamino-d-camphor.

Solvents:	MeOH.		EtOH.		Acetone.		Pyridine.		EtAc.		CHCl ₃ .		Benzene.	
	Conc. (g/100 c.c.):	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
	Calc. $\frac{15.84}{\lambda^2} =$	15.84	20.076	16.05	24.76	24.76	16.05	24.76	24.76	24.76	24.76	24.76	24.76	15.57
	$[\alpha]_{\lambda_1} =$	15.84	20.076	16.05	24.76	24.76	16.05	24.76	24.76	24.76	24.76	24.76	24.76	15.57
	$\lambda_1 =$	0.3128	0.2668	0.2775	0.2921	0.2775	0.2921	0.2775	0.2921	0.2775	0.2921	0.2775	0.2921	0.2953
Lines	ϕ	$[\alpha]$	$[\alpha]$	$[\alpha]$	$[\alpha]$									
	ϕ	c	c	c	c									
L _{157m}	45.0	45.00	53.0	52.98	58.0	58.05	44.0*	44.00	64.5	64.52	65.5	65.49	43.0	44.99
C _{41m}	50.0	50.03	59.0	58.45	64.5	62.32	49.0	48.74	72.0	71.09	72.5	72.28	48.5	47.66
L _{149m}	57.0	57.59	66.0	66.61	73.0	72.78	56.0	55.58	81.0	80.35	83.0	82.37	54.5	54.69
N _{162m}	64.0	63.54	73.0	72.71	80.5	80.13	61.5	61.28	87.5	88.14	90.0	89.95	60.0	60.02
H _{167m}	67.0	67.07	77.0	76.33	83.5	84.22	64.5	64.49	92.5	92.43	93.5	94.43	64.0	63.34
A _{168m}	79.0	78.77	88.0	88.10	99.0	97.52	75.0	75.09	104.0	103.40	110.5	109.00	72.5	73.72
L _{169m}	79.0	79.11	87.0	88.41	98.0	97.78	75.0	75.39	106.5	106.80	109.5	109.40	73.5	73.98
A _{169m}	91.0	91.37	102.0	100.30	112.5	111.40	87.0	86.28	122.5	120.70	125.5	124.90	85.0	84.84
C _{169m}	98.0	98.60	108.0	107.10	118.5	119.20	92.0	94.34	128.0	128.70	132.5	132.60	91.0	91.80
C _{170m}	118.0	119.60	128.0	126.10	143.0	141.10	103.0	100.06	149.5	150.00	158.0	156.20	108.5	109.10
C _{171m}	131.0	131.10	146.0	145.90	159.5	159.70	119.5	120.10	161.0	162.30	170.0	168.50	120.0	118.80
L _{171m}	140.0	139.10	143.0	142.80	162.5	160.80	128.5	126.00	170.0	170.00	177.0	166.70	123.5	125.16
H _{172m}	172.0	172.00	168.0	168.90	191.5	191.60	152.5	153.30	200.0	200.00	209.5	209.50	152.0	152.40

TABLE V
m-Chlorophenylamino-*d*-camphor.

Solvents:	MeOH.	EtOH.	Acetone.	Pyridine.	Etac.	CHCl ₃	Benzene.
(Conc. g./100 c.c.):	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
Calc. } [α] λ _D }	= $\frac{25.815}{\lambda^2 - 0.04665}$	= $\frac{25.56}{\lambda^2 - 0.05964}$	= $\frac{25.76}{\lambda^2 - 0.05971}$	= $\frac{9.60}{\lambda^2 - 0.0911}$	= $\frac{29.94}{\lambda^2 - 0.05725}$	= $\frac{28.34}{\lambda^2 - 0.09367}$	= $\frac{26.55}{\lambda^2 - 0.08826}$
	= $\frac{0.2159}{0.2442}$		= $\frac{0.23807}{0.2442}$	= $\frac{0.3017}{0.2442}$	= $\frac{0.2392}{0.2442}$	= $\frac{0.30605}{0.2442}$	= $\frac{0.29708}{0.2442}$
Lines.	[α]. o c	[α]. o c	[α]. o c	[α]. o c	[α]. o c	[α]. o c	[α]. o c
L ₁ 1208	64.0	65.5	65.46	27.0	76.0	79.5	73.5
C ₁ 1208	70.0	72.0	72.01	29.5	83.0	87.6	81.0
L ₁ 1414	79.0	82.0	81.68	34.5	94.95	102.0	93.42
N ₁ 1414	86.0	89.5	88.65	38.0	103.40	112.5	102.5
H ₁ 1510	90.0	94.0	93.09	40.0	108.50	117.5	107.0
A ₁ 1510	102.0	105.5	105.30	46.5	123.0	138.0	126.0
H ₁ 1611	103.0	107.0	106.70	46.5	123.5	139.0	126.5
A ₁ 1611	115.0	120.0	120.00	53.0	141.0	159.0	144.0
C ₁ 1611	122.0	128.5	127.60	56.5	149.0	169.5	155.0
C ₁ 1718	141.0	150.5	148.40	70.0	172.0	207.4	188.5
C ₁ 1718	148.0	149.00	158.90	76.5	184.5	225.0	201.5
L ₁ 1813	158.0	156.30	166.10	82.0	192.5	240.0	215.0
H ₁ 1916	180.0	180.20	196.01	98.0	225.5	294.1	260.0

TABLE VI

p-Chlorophenylamino-*d*-camphor.

Solvents:	MeOH.	EtOH.	Acetone.	Pyridine.	EtAc.	CHCl ₃ .	Benzene.
λ_0	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\alpha] \\ \theta \end{array} \right.$						
	0.5000	0.5000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
	$\frac{24.784}{\lambda^2 - 0.0301}$	$\frac{24.42}{\lambda^2 - 0.04965}$	$\frac{24.570}{\lambda^2 - 0.0600}$	$\frac{12.206}{\lambda^2 - 0.07425}$	$\frac{23.58}{\lambda^2 - 0.0762}$	$\frac{26.04}{\lambda^2 - 0.0577}$	$\frac{25.85}{\lambda^2 - 0.08366}$
	$\lambda_0 = \frac{0.1734}{0.2428}$	$\frac{0.2228}{0.2774}$	$\frac{0.2449}{0.2766}$	$\frac{0.2724}{0.2766}$	$\frac{0.2766}{0.2766}$	$\frac{0.2402}{0.2766}$	$\frac{0.2893}{0.2766}$
Lines.	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\alpha] \\ \theta \end{array} \right.$						
L ₁ and L ₂	59.0	61.0	62.99	32.5	63.0	69.5	70.5
C ₁ and C ₂	65.0	67.0	70.99	36.5	69.5	77.0	78.5
L ₁ and L ₂	73.0	76.0	78.61	41.0	79.0	88.0	89.5
N ₁ and N ₂	79.0	82.0	85.50	45.0	87.0	96.0	98.0
H ₁ and H ₂	81.0	85.0	89.66	46.5	90.2	99.0	102.50
A ₁ and A ₂	93.0	98.0	102.80	54.0	105.0	116.70	120.00
H ₁ and H ₂	93.0	98.0	103.10	54.5	105.0	117.10	120.50
A ₁ and A ₂	102.0	110.0	116.20	62.5	119.5	133.20	137.80
C ₁ and C ₂	109.0	115.0	123.70	65.5	129.5	142.50	147.90
C ₁ and C ₂	123.0	137.0	144.30	76.0	152.0	168.50	176.20
C ₁ and C ₂	131.0	146.0	154.70	83.0	167.0	182.00	191.40
L ₁ and L ₂	140.0	152.0	161.80	88.5	174.0	191.50	201.80
H ₁ and H ₂	155.0	174.0	189.00	105.5	208.5	228.0	243.20

We reserve the work of correlating the 'characteristic' wave-lengths (λ_0) deduced from optical rotatory dispersion equations of Drude and the 'characteristic' ultraviolet absorption maxima (λ_{max}) by direct measurements.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

These compounds were prepared and purified according to the methods described by us (Singh and Seth, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 491). The rotatory dispersion determinations were made at 35° in seven solvents for 13 wave-lengths of the visible spectrum ($\lambda = 6708\text{\AA}$ to $4358\text{\AA}$) and are recorded in Tables I-VII. The values of λ_0 , calculated from the dispersion formulae, are also recorded in the tables and are expressed as μ or 10^{-4} cm.

The authors wish to make grateful acknowledgements for the provision of research facilities by the Banaras Hindu University, and for the award of a Research Assistantship to one of them (Miss. S. K. Seth).

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY RESEARCH SECTION,
BANARAS HINDU UNIVERSITY,
BANARAS-5.

Received March 20, 1956.